
Youth as Guardians of Ancient Wisdom for Well-Being and Social Stability in the Modern Complex World- Case Study of Heartfulness Youth Training

Dr. N. Sumati¹, Dr Yamini Karmarkar²

¹Heartfulness Research Centre Mysuru, sumatinag@hotmail.com; Contact number: 9717066672

²International Institute of Professional Studies DAVV, Indore; ykarmarkar@gmail.com; Contact number: 9826022674

Abstract: Youth as guardians of ancient wisdom for social wellbeing and stability in the modern complex world is a significant aspect of the road that society takes towards a better future. The youth can be the harbinger of a stable social order based on values and life skills. The new mode would be able to project the progressive and developed country that India can stand for and share globally in an attempt to strengthen humanity and social integration. The way to this development would be the training of the youth in values beneficial to them and would percolate entire community. Training would necessarily involve spiritual values as laid down in ancient literature and adapted to the complexities of human existence in the present era. Yoga, meditation and aspects of gurukula from ancient principles and practice were found to have a modern scientific base in the youth training in heartfulness. These values help the individual in their self-development goals and also further to spread these ideals through role of the youth in volunteer service and in group activities.

The present research is the case study of heartfulness youth development programmes that precisely rest on the ancient Yogic wisdom, service orientation and group participation by youth for sharing these ancient valuable ideals.

The research methodology on this study relied on both qualitative as well as quantitative techniques. Phenomenology for the independent study of youth training programmes through the observation of the social phenomenon as it occurred at ground level was employed. Survey method for study on volunteer service among the youth for their contribution to social intelligence was the focus. Based on the philosophy of the founders and present global leader and guide of heartfulness, the meditation and prescribed practice of Heartfulness threw light on the experiential and scientific foundation of the goals of youth training. The youth participation in training module at kanha shantivanam campus of Heartfulness was the powerful tool for national and global social harmony and wellbeing goals.

Keywords: ancient wisdom, heartfulness, youth training, social intelligence, social stability.

Introduction

In this research paper, the importance of ancient wisdom for society and humanity through its adaptation for the present day has been examined in the case study of heartfulness meditation and training of youth in Kanha Shantivanam. There were many items identified in the principles and practice of ancient knowledge systems and

some of the profound aspects were taken up, comparing them to the heartfulness model. Raja Yoga, meditation, gurukula, service-orientation were some of the significant features studied. Social intelligence as an important concept, and its nurturing for achievement of the desired goals were scrutinized with the help of social intelligence scales. Youth training in Heartfulness threw light on the nuances, the philosophy and the practicality of beneficial values from the history of ancient India.

The paper covers research methodology, literature review and the research findings and discussions. The implications of the study for policy, further research and development of youth has been stated; some conclusions were drawn of the research done in the heartfulness meditation and training in values and skills of the youth.

Literature Review

The important concepts taken up in the research opened a vista of the theoretical and empirical studies available in the field. The TROMSO and MESI social intelligence scales and sub-scales were used as relevant for the focus of the study. (Silvera (2001), Frankowsky (2014). Ancient ideals of gurukula were elaborated in books by Sharan, B. (1968), Balasubramaniam, K.S. (2013). Raja Yoga in the works of Vivekananda, Patanjali and Ram Chandra helped in understanding the details of yoga. Youth training in Government documents (Government of India, 2019) and in conference reports provided a history of development of youth as a category to reckon with. Literature on social change and spiritual leadership and change were also fruitfully covered.

Some features of the system of education for the youth in the Gurukula in ancient India

The main focus in the research paper being youth training and development at heartfulness, the vast literature on ancient system of gurukula was relevant for a background on youth education and training in ancient India. A holistic approach to training and education in ancient times, the gurukula where students studied under the rishis had many benefits, necessary for the modern day too. Youth benefitted much from well managed and thought-out system of education of the ancient Indian society.

Natural environment

As Ram Chandra pointed out that the rishis lived in hermitages away from the hustle and bustle of human habitation, in the forests. The students therefore lived in the natural environment. The students, Balasubramaniam stated, went to the gurukula in different age brackets as was prescribed during that time. They lived in the home of the rishis and learnt many skills. As the students became part of the guru's household, they contributed in many chores such as bringing the firewood for the household of the guru for cooking food. The students lived in close proximity to the natural surroundings and learnt to face the challenges of the environment. Students in the gurukula learnt specialized disciplines too besides the spiritual teachings from the rishi /guru. They received a holistic education to lead a complete life in the ashramas after their training in brahmacharya ashram in the gurukula.

Importance of guru or teacher

The guru was the fountain head of knowledge and was able to impart the same to the students. The guru was the one 'who leads from darkness to light'. (Balasubramaniam, K.S., 2013, p71). "The Veda says 'Maatru devo bhava, pitru devo bhava, aacharya devo bhava, atithi devo bhava' Consider your mother as God, your father as God, your teacher as God and your guest as God". (Rajagopalachari, P., 2004b, p.114). They taught the Vedas to the students in the traditional way of shravana, manana and nidhidhyasana. Reading, thinking over it and meditating or absorbing what was taught. In this process the learning happened for the students. They could excel in different disciplines. Sharan lists the many disciplines covered in various ashramas of the rishis. For example, astronomy, ayurveda, archery, logic, law, mathematic and other arts and science disciplines. The rishis used to have many discussions with experts in the king's court and during festivals. Spirituality came first according to Ram Chandra, and rishis gave priority to spiritual progress and achievements before they shared and served the community and society.

According to the rishis, the purusharthas was the goal of life and these principles were followed by the rishis and the same was taught to the brahmacharis in gurukulas. As moksha was the ultimate goal the students were taught all the virtues to be imbibed by them and followed all their lives. These principles and values included "truth in action, doing of good deeds, the doing of justice, the performance of duty, the observance of law, both human and divine." (Sharan, B. 1968, p48-49). Foundation of virtues were laid for the students in the gurukula that were hard work, purity, righteousness, obedience, humility and service-mindedness. Education was based on the sacred texts

or the shastras. Gyana was by eliciting answers from the student. The gyana in the Upanishads spoke of the understanding by the student where the light came from and in the process of answering questions. they arrived at the answer that the inner light is the guiding factor for human beings. Thus inner light helped acquire knowledge, and enlightenment and it was through experiences.

Method of Learning

The three steps in the learning process at the gurukula or the guru's household or hermitage was shravana, manana and nidhidhyasana. "The ancient knowledge says there are three steps to knowledge or to understanding or to awakening. One is listening about it – shravana, second is to think about it, ruminate over it, mull over it – manana. And then to establish the result of all that you have meditated, mulled about something, in yourself as part of you - nidhidhyasana." (Rajagopalachari, P., 2004b, p.76). The gurukulas developed in the later period into developed universities like Nalanda and Taxila. Therefore the idea of gurukula was a wide spectrum.

Life skills

The gurukula prepared the student to enter all stages or ashramas of life as all four stages required ethical discipline. The grihastha ashrama or the role of householder was a sacred environment for cultivating all good values. Sharan pointed out that in ancient India, the home was "the school of unselfishness, compassion, tenderness, temperance, helpfulness, prudence, industry, right judgement and clarity" (Sharan, B., 1968, p.55). In Heartfulness the philosophy on the importance of grihastha ashrama or the householder's life as seen in the works of Ram Chandra of Fatehgarh was: the home as the training ground where patience, tolerance and endurance were learnt. (Ram Chandra, 2019, p. xxxiii).

Spirituality, science and knowledge

"There is wisdom in the ways of ancient India. In ancient times, scientists were all saints: they were philosophers and yogis both. First of all they attempted God. When they felt that they were realized, then they attempted other things for the good of the world. They gave attention to their own making and only afterwards they sought the ways of making others. When approached this way, science can be useful. After realizing the Goal they took up this work for the betterment of others." (Ram Chandra, 2015, p.114). Scholarly work like Yantra Sarvasva in Sanskrit, knowledge of weight of stars, drawing and planning flying machines of rishi Bhardwaj, show the great scientific knowledge of the ancient sages. The scientific knowledge of pushpak viman and agniban of Ramayana and Mahabharata were examples as seen in the epic period. Ram Chandra explains that "when the sages had gained spirituality, then they attempted other things. This way, thinking first became correct as a result of practice, and they were able to come to the right judgment. Only then did they go towards science." (Ram Chandra, 2015, p.116).

Bhagwat Gita

The importance of doing one's duty as laid down in the Gita was emphasized by Ram Chandra, the founder of the modern day Heartfulness method of meditation. Duty was so crucial for human beings to follow since it "constitutes the very basis of the social order of the world." As duty 'falls within the scope of Raja yoga', it was vital for 'cessation of samskaras' according to Ram Chandra and, helpful for the spiritual evolution of human beings. (Ram Chandra, 1992, p.247).

Raja Yoga

Ram Chandra stated that Raja Yoga was the ancient system and science that the great saints in ancient India practiced to realize God. The system of the rishis existed much before the period of Ramayana. Raja Yoga was about human mind and its immense potential and Ram Chandra compared it to the 'Kshobh' or the 'primary stir' that led to the entire creation. That was the power of the mind which was limitless. (Ram Chandra, 2013b, p.121). The ancient sage who was the originator of Raja Yoga, was there seventy-two generations before Raja Dasharath. Knowing the immense power of the mind, Ram Chandra stated that the ancient sage utilized the power of thought that was available to the human being for training. That is where Raja Yoga originated and it was 'the king of the yogas.' (Ram Chandra, 2013b, p.122).

The Raja Yoga practiced was an inner approach; it utilized the mind to refine the mind. Being an internal process in the practice of meditation, Swami Vivekananda explained that "the power of attention, when properly guided, and directed towards the internal world, will analyze the mind and illuminate facts for us." (Swami Vivekananda, 2016, p.58). Rajagopalachari elucidated that 'an externalized search leads nowhere, whereas turning the mind

inwards leads us to the goal of our search' and therefore 'this is a very good scientific reason as to why we should meditate'. (Rajagopalachari, P., 2016a, p.33).

Heartfulness

The founders of heartfulness were intent on bringing the ancient wisdom of spirituality for the masses. The 'long-forgotten spiritual science' and to give it for people in the complex world in terms of 'practical knowledge and perception was the vital aspect of heartfulness meditation and practice. "It was thus for the spiritual regeneration of humanity and the emancipation of the pining souls that the great Master came down to help the masses on the Divine path through the old yogic process of Pranahuti". (Ram Chandra, 2019), p.182).

"Mere reading of books without a close study of the heart's book is of no avail." (Ram Chandra 1992, p. 324). According to Socrates, 'Knowledge is virtue' and here virtue indicated a state marked by desirelessness. Ram Chandra of Shahjahanpur stated that desirelessness was the 'essence of education'. "If by acquiring high education one comes up to that level, I think the purpose of education is served, and that is a spiritual stage." (Ram Chandra, 1992, p.325).

Research Methodology

The research used both qualitative methods and quantitative methodology for the purpose of collecting data to arrive at results. The phenomenological approach enabled an in-depth study of several aspects in the youth training in Heartfulness as organized at their main campus in Kanha Shantivanam. The timetable and schedule followed was observed by the researcher staying in residence with the youth participants. Details were noted in a diary and the data collected was analysed and interpreted for the study. A purposive sample was the youth participants who came to the training program. They came willingly and with due permission of their parents as the age bracket of the youth was 15-24 years, what was the official definition of youth by the UNESCO. A survey was conducted by using a well-prepared Questionnaire that the youth had to fill up. The Questionnaire had three sections, for personal information, on volunteer service and to study social intelligence using the scales developed in the TROMSO and MESI social intelligence scales and sub-scales. The Questionnaires were uniformly administered when the youth came together for classroom session. The researcher was present and collected all the filled-out Questionnaires from the youth participants. Around 600 of 700 Questionnaires were duly filled and were used for statistical analysis.

A conceptual framework was drawn up and the main parameters for analysis in the study were included. The relationship between social intelligence and group activities and volunteer service in the heartfulness meditation training was the relationship between the core concepts.

Conceptual Framework of Heartfulness youth training

Research Findings and Discussions

The program was a residential one and the youth were provided dormitories for stay, separate for girls and boys. Being in residence gave its own special flavour as to how the group leaders interacted with the youth; what the problems were that the youth had to face and how discipline was maintained by the youth. The qualitative study enabled the development of a matrix on how the inputs for the youth participants in the well-structured training program was done.

Basic Structure of youth training program

The basic structure was seen in the youth programs: detox- electronic gadgets like mobiles and laptops were not used by the youth during the training period; meditation – this was an important part of individual and group activity; time-management – proper and clear schedule of timings for all activities; meditation, meals, sleep, classes) were laid down; volunteer service – opportunities for service were provided in the training module.

Meditation

The training included heartfulness meditation and the youth woke up early to meditate and do their individual practice of sadhana. The youth also participated in the group meditation that was organized for all daily at kanha shanthivanam. The prescribed practice of meditation as laid down by the founders of heartfulness needs to be seen for its philosophy and practical aspects. Heartfulness meditation was derived from the ancient practise of Raja Yoga, that is, the king of the yogas for the regulation of the mind. The mind was used to regulate the mind as Swami Vivekananda explained. The practical aspects of the meditation system of heartfulness could be seen elaborated in the ten maxims, a commentary on which was written by Ram Chandra. It emphasized rising up before dawn and doing meditation with a heart full of love and devotion and with due regard to purity of body and mind. The goal was to be fixed as complete oneness with God. Evening cleaning for half hour to remove the burden of the day's accumulations, and night at bedtime to offer prayer to beg forgiveness for any wrongs committed, resolving not to repeat. Daily to practice a prayer for 15 minutes from 9 to 9.15pm a universal prayer that people all over the world are becoming peace-loving. Other aspects included for spiritual progress included treating everyone as brethren, not being revengeful in nature, accepting everything as a gift from God, eating in constant divine thought with due regard to honest and pious earnings. (Annexure 1)

Time management

The Youth training program being a residential one, the time table was set for the youth making it easier to do all their work on time, right from getting up early by 4.30 am when the bell would ring and they started the day from their morning meditation. The time for group meditation, meals were fixed having a disciplined schedule for the youth; and sleep by 9.30pm when the bell rang in kanha shanthivanam. The scientific significance of timely and nutritious meals; and enough number of hours of sound sleep at night after doing the night prayer in their beds was part of this time management and discipline, a skill and a lifestyle for the youth to adopt at their age and make it a life-long learning.

Digital-Detox

The youth were free without their mobiles and laptops during their training period. They were aware of this requirement when they were given the brochure regarding the training even before they arrived for the program. The youth duly complied and some were reluctant but could give up after a day into the training. However, when the training program ended they collected their electronic gadgets, and many reported feeling reluctant to take back their mobiles. The activities during their training was in a serene and green natural environment of the heartfulness campus with digital detox.

Volunteer Service

Service opportunities were provided during the program. The benefits of volunteer service in the literature, as being a stress buster, joyful, good for meeting and learning from others, helping others by listening and having empathy were experienced at the ground level. The youth could choose the activities of their liking like photography, culinary activities, tool room management, organic farming cleaning environment eg. Collecting dried leaves for compost and could work in teams, to learn new skills, or to improve or enhance knowledge, and learning team spirit.

Dynamic structure of youth training program

Besides the basic structure was the dynamic structure in the training program where group activities, as also new activities were included in different youth seminars and trainings. Volunteer service activities also varied from one to another program. The classroom sessions were different with dynamic and changing topics covered, new topics of interest to the youth added; and there were varying speakers and experts coming in for the topics covered. Composition of the youth seminars also varied; regional training program for the youth had participants from different parts of the country; international seminars were different with youth participants from many countries; one program had NSS (National Service Scheme) participants from the government program who already had experience in social service and came with their team leaders and the interactions were well structured; in one program the local Telengana students from a particular institution joined the youth training and shared their knowledge on trees and ecology while learning the heartfulness meditation for the first time. Themes chosen for the programs also were different, for example, 'acceptance', 'expectation'. The creative activities also changed from seminar to seminar, like music program by the youth group, poetry inspired by saints and philosophy in another youth program.

Social Intelligence Outcomes and Essences from the youth training program

The inputs, outcomes and the essences of the phenomenology of the youth training program was analyzed and a matrix was designed to simplify and understand the social intelligence outcomes and essences. The youth training program nurtured social intelligence through the enhancement of social awareness, social skills, social harmony, empathy, compassion, social tolerance, group cohesion and team spirit and unity.

Social Intelligence Essences in Heartfulness Youth Training Program

S. No.	Input (For youth participants in training)	Outcomes (For youth participants completing the training)	Essences (From youth training seminars widening social intelligence)
1.	Direct Inputs		
	1. meditation	1. Awareness, harmony	1. Social awareness, inspiration
	2. themes	2. youth aspiration, development	2. social tolerance, compassion
	3. stories of saints	3. appreciating social values	3. social inspiration, awareness
	4. classroom sessions	4. scientific approach to spiritual values	4. social logic, navigation, negotiation, manipulation
2.	Subtle Inputs		
	1. Daily timetable	1. Discipline, time management	1. Social skills
	2. team leaders (SPOCs)	2. management of groups / group activities	2. group cohesion, sense of belonging
	3. Communication and leadership	3. capacity building; development of leadership qualities, values	3. group advancement, team spirit
	4. collaborations (NSS)	4. cooperation, mutual learning	4. social awareness
3.	Experiential Learning		
	1. Heartfulness Campus Residency	1. Co-existence, sharing, adjustment	1. Social Harmony
	2. Group activities	2. common goals achievement	2. Social information skills
	3. Volunteer work	3. social service	3. Empathy, compassion

Survey Findings

The data collected from the survey of the youth participants on the TROMSO and MESI social intelligence scales yielded outcomes of higher social intelligence. A comparison of social awareness and manipulation subscales across different youth age groups showed higher social awareness among the younger participants in the age-group of 15 to 17 years who were basically school goers compared to the higher bracket youth. The manipulation or negotiation skills of the higher age bracket youth in the category of 18 to 22 years was higher, mostly college and university students. A comparison of social awareness and empathy sub scales across different youth

volunteering experience groups showed that social awareness and empathy were higher among persons who had experience of volunteer service in comparison to those youth who had no experience of volunteer service. Comparing social skills, empathy and social awareness sub scales revealed that social skills, empathy and social awareness was seen higher among those who had more than two years of volunteer service in comparison to those with less than two years or no experience at all of volunteer work. (Annexure 2A, 2B, 2C).

The percentage-wise response of youth towards 'application of learnings' from group activities of heartfulness was high for various parameters like cleanliness, respecting diversity, discipline, communication, attitude to serve, environmental consciousness, dignity of labour, empathy, simplicity at work, interpersonal interaction, time management and living in minimal resources. (Annexure 3). The youth carried these skills and lifelong learnings into other social groups.

Around eighty per cent of the youth had no formal training in volunteer work yet they had experience in volunteering service. The family played a major part in their service orientation by providing supportive role and encouraging and inspiring them to do volunteer service. Social awareness, empathy and team spirit were nourished through volunteer service. Youth were more aware of their environment, problem-solving attitudes grew, they worked in teams in unity and cohesion to achieve group targets, and developed empathy in interactions and social awareness. Volunteer service helped to better their neighbourhood, improve and complete unfinished projects. Youth who had prior exposure to volunteer work had preferences for service in spiritual organizations, distribution of food and clothes in hospitals and education of children.

Ancient wisdom in the twenty-first century and beyond for spiritual and material wellbeing

Taking a look at some features in the ancient Indian society, it was observed that the introduction of the heartfulness meditation system reignited the benefits of raja yoga meditation for the benefit of the people by making the practical aspects simpler and easy to follow along with the busy schedules that people often have due to pressures of work, family and commitments. Kanha shanthivanam displayed a need for being closer to Nature as the environment was natural and calm for meditative pursuits. Emphasis on duty was revealed in the time schedules. It was the duty towards oneself and others were important to follow. Volunteer service was a partner with meditation as it had the benefit of service based on the values that heartfulness emphasized, for example, honesty and truth, humility, compassion, hard work and excellence, desirelessness, helpfulness, right thinking and correct understanding, and being non-judgmental. The grihastha ashrama has been clearly stated as the training ground for penance and love as the cornerstone for heartfulness and for spiritual evolution. Social intelligence and inspiration were nurtured in Heartfulness practical methods that were experiential in nature. The qualities and values were vital for success in the workplace, in the neighbourhood, in the family, in all social groups and organizations as well as for all institutions across society for greater harmony and social stability.

Policy and other Implications

Scope for research is very high in this area of youth training in spiritual organizations as it has a cascading effect and brings betterment in the whole society. More research should be encouraged and sponsored both in the academia and by governments and think tanks. More time series data and research could show results on the value-based need for the youth to carry it forward in their leadership roles in society. Policies need to focus on such research and outcomes on the ancient values that could be nurtured for example, as seen in the Heartfulness system, for greater peace and development of the nation and globally.

Conclusion

Youth trained in spiritual values based on scientific experiment and scientific approach as in Heartfulness not only nurture the values of ancient Indian society and wisdom, but also strengthen those values for small and large social groups and organizations. The spread of the positive values could enable the social stability and peace of the world and protect the planet and its environment for the future. The ancient wisdom reset in the Heartfulness meditation and practice, not only helped the youth trained in Kanha Shantivanam but would be a pointer to leadership of the youth in small and big social groups and in their global leadership for social well-being and wellness and in creating a stable social order for the nation and the world.

References

- [1]. Atal, Y., (2005) "Youth in Asia", pp. 9-21 in 'Youth in Transition – The Challenges of Generational Change in Asia' - Proceedings of the 15th Biennial General Conference Association of Asian Social Science Research Councils (edited) by Fay Gale and Stephanie Fahey.
- [2]. Balasubramaniam, K.S., (2013) "God in the Vedas and the Upanishads" pp.456-472 in "Proceedings of the First Seminar", August 19 -23, 2006, Sahaj Marg Spirituality Foundation India.
- [3]. Govt. of India, (2019) Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports, Annual Report, 2018-19. <https://yas.nic.in/documents/annual-report>
- [4]. Frankovsky, M., and Birknerova, Z., (2014) "Measuring Social Intelligence- The MESI Methodology", in *Asian Social Science*, 10 (6), 90-97. ISSN 1911-2017. <https://doi:10.5539/ass.v10n6p90>
- [5]. Rajagopalachari, P., (2004a) "Youth: A time of Promise and for Effort. Volume II: A Guided Life", ISBN 81-7894-068-X.
- [6]. Rajagopalachari, P. (2004b) "Sharing with the Universe " A talk given by Shri Parthasarathi Rajagopalachari on 3rd October, 2004 at Bangalore <http://www.sahajmarg.org/literature/online/speeches/sharing-with-the-universe>. retrieved 4 July 2017
- [7]. Ram Chandraji, (Lalaji), (2019) "Truth Eternal". Translated by Lakshmi Shankar. Shri Ram Chandra Mission, India ISBN 978-93-88095-16-7
- [8]. Rajagopalachari, P., (2015) "Heart of education", (1st ed.) Kolkata: Spiritual Hierarchy Publication Trust. ISBN 978-93-84963-43-9.
- [9]. Ram Chandra, (1985) "Autobiography of Ram Chandra Volume II".
- [10]. Ram Chandra, (2013a) "Reality at Dawn" in "Complete Works of Ram Chandra, Volume 1". Kolkata: Spiritual Hierarchy Publication Trust ISBN 978-93-80335-04-9.
- [11]. Ram Chandra, (2013b) "The Efficacy of Raja Yoga in the Light of Sahaj Marg", pp.115-171, in "Complete Works of Ram Chandra, Volume I. Kolkata: Spiritual Hierarchy Publication Trust. ISBN 978-93-80335-04-9.
- [12]. Ram Chandra, (2015) "Complete Works of Ram Chandra, Volume V", Kolkata: Spiritual Hierarchy Publication Trust. ISBN 978-93-84963-13-2
- [13]. Rajagopalachari, P., (2015) "Heart of education", (1st ed.) Kolkata: Spiritual Hierarchy Publication Trust. ISBN 978-93-84963-43-9.
- [14]. Rajagopalachari, P., (2016a) in Heartfulness June p.30. Spiritual Hierarchy Publication Trust.
- [15]. Rajagopalachari, P., (2016b) "In His Footsteps 1981 to 1983", Kolkata: Spiritual Hierarchy Publication Trust.
- [16]. Rajagopalachari, P., (2018) "My Master", Kolkata : Spiritual Hierarchy Publication Trust ISBN 978-93-83516-01-8
- [17]. Ram Chandra, (1985) "Autobiography of Ram Chandra Volume II".
- [18]. Ram Chandra, (1992) "Complete Works of Ram Chandra" Volume 2, and (Voice Real), Shahjahanpur: Shri Ram Chandra Mission. ISBN 81-85177-46-5.
- [19]. Ram Chandra, (2007) "Sahaj Marg Philosophy" in 'Complete Works of Ram Chandra Volume 1'.
- [20]. Ram Chandra, (2000) "Complete Works of Ram Chandra Volume I", 2000.
- [21]. Ram Chandra, (2012) "Commentary on Ten Maxims of Sahaj Marg". Kolkata: Spiritual Hierarchy Publication Trust. ISBN 978-93-81281-42-0
- [22]. Ram Chandra, 2019, "Complete Works of Ram Chandra Volume 2" Spiritual Hierarchy Publication Trust, Kolkata. ISBN 978-93-80335-05-6
- [23]. Sharan, B., (1968) "The Gurukula System of Education in India and Its Application to Modern Times", (Abridged Edition). Penn Community Services.
- [24]. Silvera, D. H. ,Martinussen, M., and Dahl, T.I. (2001), " TROMSO Social Intelligence Scale - A Self Report Measure of Social Intelligence", in *Scandinavian Journal of Psychology* , 42 (4), 313-319. ISSN 0036 5564. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9450.00242>
- [25]. Swami Vivekananda, (2016) "Observation" (Excerpts from the 'Introduction to Raja Yoga'), in Heartfulness, Issue 6, 55-59 Spiritual Hierarchy Publication Trust.

ANNEXURE 1

Ten Maxims

(as in Sahaj Marg/ Heartfulness)

1. "Rise before dawn. Offer your prayer and puja (meditation) at a fixed hour preferably before sunrise, sitting in one and the same pose. Have a separate place and seat for worship. Purity of body and mind should be specially adhered to."
2. "Begin your puja (meditation) with a prayer for spiritual elevation with a heart full of love and devotion."
3. "Fix your goal which should be complete oneness from God. Rest not till the ideal is achieved."
4. "Be plain and simple to be identical with Nature."
5. "Be truthful. Take miseries as Divine blessings for your own good and be thankful."
6. "Know all people as thy brethren and treat them as such."
7. Be not revengeful for the wrongs done by others. Take them with gratitude as heavenly gifts."
8. "Be happy to eat in constant Divine thought whatever you get, with due regard to honest and pious earnings."
9. "Mould your living so as to rouse a feeling of love and piety in others."
10. "At bed-time, feeling the presence of God, repent for the wrongs committed. Beg forgiveness in a supplicant mood, resolving not to allow repetition of the same."

PRAYER

"O Master!

Thou art the real goal of human life.

We are yet but slaves of wishes putting bar to our advancement.

Thou art the only God and Power to bring us up to that stage."

(p.28 "Commentary on Ten Maxims of Sahaj Marg" By Ram Chandra, 2012).

(Taken from the book, "Commentary on Ten Maxims of Sahaj Marg" by Ram Chandra (2012). It contains the practice prescribed for heartfulness meditation members and the meditation is offered free of cost. These life principles and practices are reiterated for youth trainees also during training/seminars)

ANNEXURE 2A

Social Awareness and Manipulation -A Comparison across different Youth Age-Groups

Comparison of the Means of the Different Youth Age Groups for Selected Dimensions of Social Intelligence

Classified Age		TROMSO subscale of Social Awareness	MESI subscale of Manipulation
Age 15 to 17 Years	Mean	20.28	14.99
	N	177	170.00

	Std. Deviation	4.20	5.25
	Mean	19.20	16.51
Age 18 to 22 Years	N	221	217.00
	Std. Deviation	4.44	5.41
	Mean	19.62	16.11
Age 22 to 24 Years	N	117	113.00
	Std. Deviation	4.60	5.37
	Mean	19.67	15.90
Total	N	515	500.00
	Std. Deviation	4.41	5.38

ANNEXURE 2B

Social Awareness and Empathy A Comparison across the different Youth Volunteering Experience Groups

Different Experience Groups of youth for Significant Social Intelligence Subscales- Comparison of the Means

Experience of volunteer work		TROMSO Social Awareness	MESI Empathy
Yes	Mean	20.00	23.14
	N	340	335
	Std. Deviation	4.46	4.91
No	Mean	19.01	22.19
	N	175	175
	Std. Deviation	4.26	5.38
Total	Mean	19.66	22.81
	N	515	510
	Std. Deviation	4.41	5.09

ANNEXURE 2C

Social Skills, Social Awareness and Empathy across Youth groups with different duration of volunteering experience - A Comparison

Different Duration of Volunteer Work for Significant Social Intelligence Subscales - A Comparison of Means

Duration of Volunteer service		TROMSO Social Skills	TROMSO Social Awareness	MESI Empathy
No Experience of Volunteer Work	Mean	23.16	18.89	22.14
	N	177.00	178.00	177.00
	Std. Deviation	4.04	4.24	5.37
Less than 2 years of Volunteer Work	Mean	22.71	19.35	22.56
	N	180.00	179.00	176.00

	Std. Deviation	4.12	4.20	5.10
	Mean	23.93	20.90	23.86
More than 2 years of Volunteer Work	N	158.00	158.00	157.00
	Std. Deviation	3.89	4.59	4.62
	Mean	23.24	19.67	22.82
Total	N	515.00	515.00	510.00
	Std. Deviation	4.04	4.41	5.10

ANNEXURE 3

Application of Learnings from Heartfulness Youth Training

